

IJMSBR

<https://www.ijmsbr.com/>

Impact Factor: 6.049

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.

The Research on the Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth in Somalia

Author Details: Shafie Abdirahman Digale

Wu Cheng Qu, Jin Hua Shi, Zhe Jiang Sheng, China, 321017

Department of International Economics and Trade, university of Zhejiang Normal University, China.

This paper is funded by the general project of China's National Social Science Foundation (19BJY190).

Email:shaaficidigaale49@gmail.com

KEYWORDS

ABSTRACT

Foreign Direct Investment, Economic Growth, Somalia.

The purpose of this paper aim to examine the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth of Somalia. The study utilizes time series data over the period of 2000-2018. The Data was collected from the World Bank and SESRIC organization. Organization of Islamic countries forum, especially statistical, economic and social research. To evidence the relationship between the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Somalia and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Inflation Rate (INF) and Domestic Investment (DI). This research used the augmented Dickey–Fuller [ADF], Philips– Perron [PP] to test for stationarity of the variables and Ordinary Least Square model was examined among dependent variable and independent variable. The result reveals that FDI has a positive and significant effect on Somalia economic growth. Also the result shows that inflation has negative relationship and significant impact on Somalia economic growth. While Gross Domestic Investment has a positive relationship and significant effect on Somalia economic growth. Therefore, the study recommends there is a need for the government must retain right monetary and fiscal policies and train the Somali employee in order to attract in the Somalia economy.

本文的目的是研究外国直接投资对索马里经济增长的影响。文章基于 2000 年至 2018 年期间的时序数据，并基于扩张的迪基·福勒 (ADF)，菲利普斯·佩隆(PP)和普通最小二乘法模型对因变量和自变量之间平稳性的检验，研究索马里国内生产总值 (GDP)和外国直接投资(FDI)，通货膨胀率(INF)和国内投资(DI)之间的关系。所有数据均来源于世界银行 (WB)，伊斯兰国家统计、经济和社会研究和培训中心(SESRIC)和伊斯兰国家组织论坛中关于统计、经济和社会研究的报告。结果表明，外商直接投资、国内投资总额对索马里经济增长具有显著的正向影响，而通货膨胀则对索马里经济增长具有显著的负向影响。据此，研究建议政府必须维持正确的货币和财政政策，培训索马里员工，以促进索马里经济增长。

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research Background

The impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth has been a fascinating topic for many decades. Firms in all industries are expanding their activities through foreign direct investment than always before in both developed and developing countries. Foreign direct investment has played a crucial role in the African economy and the policymaker claims that foreign direct investment increases host countries' competitiveness and boosts growth. Foreign direct investment is a direct investment into production or business in a country by an individual or company of another country, either by purchasing a company in the target country or by extending operations of an established firm in that country. Foreign direct investment in Africa is seen to be more of a requirement to foster development. The key factor for this is that FDI is helping to solve the two big challenges faced by most African countries with inadequate infrastructure and expertise and the savings deficit, which in turn lowers poverty levels and increases living standards. Foreign direct investment is a very significant force affecting world economic growth and, in particular, Somalia is seeking to monitor the level of foreign direct investment for economic growth. Most recent thirty years shifted FDI inflow of Somalia. In Somalia probably the most African full who need greater investment in light of the fact that having more natural resources.

The role of foreign direct investment in the mechanism of economic development has long been the subject of intensive discussion. Although the debate has given wealthy perceptions into the link between foreign direct investment and development, there is very little analytical study of the problem. FDI is one example of multinational factor movements that control responsibility for business undertaking in one nation by an association situated in another nation. Foreign direct investment, an inactive investment in shares of another country for example, public stocks and securities, is isolated from portfolio foreign investment by the component of control.

The Strongest positives of adoption FDI is the rise in gross production, increased opportunities of employment, further outflow of exchange and exports of technological advancement between the Investors and countries. Developing and underdeveloped nations are reliant on monetarily developed nations for monetary help to accomplish the financial dependability. Developed nations do their interests in various areas particularly in powerless areas of the economy where the host nation needs more assets to set up those areas. Developed countries are eager to exploit their investment, and host countries are enabled to improve their weak areas and generate more open doors for business. The Objective of This Paper Aim to Investigate the Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth of Somalia. More Specifically, It Aims To Determine The Performance Of Foreign Direct Investment And Its Contribution To Economic Growth In Somalia.

1.2. Problem Statement

The Somalia government's ability to mobilize domestic capital to fund development programs has been weak in the past. FDI presents a choice to overcome this capital deficit and accelerate the country's economic growth. In this sense, the role of FDI on the economy of Somalia over the last Thirty Years should be measured in order to reveal its possible effects on economic development. The results will indicate policy areas that should be explored by the government in order to encourage the promotion of investment while ensuring positive impacts on the development of Somalia. Therefore, the government of Somalia is working on a more competitive investment program to attract foreign investments by introducing new strategies and rewards, which would not help the foreign direct investment without setting proper policies.

1.3. Significance of Problem

Investments influence economic growth. It also affects infrastructure, industry, government debt and credit, and expenditure, which in turn affects the standard of living for the populations. In theory, FDI has a huge influence on every market. However, if the effect of FDI in Somalia has been positive or negative, it has to be

decided. In the context of GDP, calculating this effect provides a basic metric that measures national competitiveness.

Therefore a regression analysis provides a better understanding of this pattern. It would be a significant to analyze whether Foreign direct investment either have a positive effect on GDP or otherwise. Either finding would shed light on the connection between FDI and Somali's economic growth and identify policy areas that need to be improved for the country's economic growth and development.

1.4. Research Question

The study was conducted to answer the following research questions.

1. What is the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth?
2. What is the impact of FDI on the economic growth of Somalia?
3. What is the current status of FDI and economic growth in Somalia?

1.5. Objective of the study

1.5.1. General objective

The major objective of the study is to establish the relationship between Foreign Direct Investment and economic growth in Somalia for the period 2000 to 2018.

1.5.2. Specific objective

- To assess the effect of FDI on the economic growth of Somalia.
- To compare the relative intensity of FDI contribution to growth with other growth determinants.
- To find out the current status of foreign direct investment and economic growth in Somalia.

1.6. Significant of the study

This study aims to investigate the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth of

Somalia. This research will be critical as in Somalia has encountered a diminishing pattern of FDI inflows over the years. It should be noticed that FDI inflow to Somalia is very critical. Because it functions as an origin of capital, and considering that foreign assistance has been decreasing over the years. For the light of the carrying out for this study would be beneficiaries for the following groups. The government of Somalia, particularly the ministries of commerce and planning involved and busy of the economic growth and attraction of foreign investors.

Researchers: this study will be beneficiary for every researcher who want to know something about foreign direct investment and its effect of economic growth.

The domestic investors: also this study would be beneficiary for the domestic investors because the researcher would try to discover whether the FDI is good or bad for Somalia economic growth. Last but not least local communities this research is also important for the local communities to wake up the problems that may face their economic activities and the pro and cons of the foreign direct investment.

1.7. Scope of the Study

The aim of the study is to analyze the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth in Somalia. The analysis was also delimited to the period covered between 2000 and 2018, as the latest data are more valuable and better suited to the applicable recommendations.

1.8. Outline of the study

This thesis is organized in five chapters. Chapter one will introduce Research Background,

Statement of the problem, Significance of Problem, Research Question, Significance of the study, Objective of the study, Scope of the Study and finally outline of the study. Chapter two will be about a review of literature. The Concept of FDI, Concept of Economic growth, theoretical research on the effect of FDI on Economic Growth and Empirical research on the effect of FDI on Economic growth. Chapter Three discusses Somalia's Economy and the role of FDI in Somalia.

Chapter Four. Will describes the methodology, Data collection, Method of data analysis, and Model specification. Chapter Five presents Analysis. Time series Analysis, Regression Results, Discussion. Chapter Six will presents a Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations for Future Research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Concept and Definitions of FDI

Foreign Direct Investment. According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the FDI applies to investments made in order to gain permanent interest in businesses existing outside the investor's economy (Ridgeway, 2004). The IMF therefore finds an investment to be listed as an FDI if the creditor owns at least 10% of the partial equity share and maintains a considerable amount of management power. This is analogous to the manner in which FDI is established by the organization of economic cooperation and Development (OECD).

According to the OECD, (2012). A foreign direct investment enterprise is a company occupant in one economy in which an investor occupant in another economy retains 10% or more of its voting rights, directly or indirectly, whether incorporated or similar to a firm resident in economy. An ownership of at least than percent of the company's voting power is deemed to be the required proof that the investor has adequate leverage to have an important voice in its management One common criterion of identifying an investment as an FDI from the definitions of the IMF and the OECD is that the ownership of the founder must be at least 10 percent, which is also a condition for the corporation to have considerable influence.

2.2. Concept of Economic Growth

According to Nekipelov (2011). Economic growth is the phenomenon of the amount of ultimate goods and services generated throughout the chosen time unit ('the aggregate product'). There are various definitions and methods of calculating economic growth, but the central idea is that of growth in the economy's long-term productive potential, usually calculated by real growth in Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The Gross Domestic Product is determined as the amount of goods and services purchased over time in a country, without double counting of the goods used in other outputs. The production of consumption products and resources, including government services, and investment products is a quantitative indicator (Lequiller, 2004).

Measures of economic growth include GDP, per capita national income, Changes in the natural resource base, the pace of formation of wealth, demographic composition, technology , scientific and technical expertise , skills and results, administrative or organizational nature, the structure of the market for products, the degree and pattern of distribution of profits, population size and composition, consumption patterns, living standards and In social relationship trends and moral dogmas and theories. The most commonly used per capita national income, however, acts as a simple indicator of a change in economic wellbeing by an increase in per capita income.

2.3. The Theoretical research on the effect of FDI on Economic Growth

The relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth has drawn considerable interest from researchers and developing-country governments. As economic growth is one of the main focus areas, foreign direct investment appeal related policies have been prioritized during the process of economic growth and development in these countries (VO, 2019).

Silajdzic and Mehic (2015) found that by contributing to the total fixed capital development and indirectly by contributing to awareness storage, FDI is presumed to directly influence economic growth. More importantly, FDI is projected to have a significant influence on economic growth under the conventional system, as FDI is presumed to complement domestic investment and is sensed to be an essential addition to capital and revenue shortages. Further research found that through information spillovers in transition countries, FDI has a substantial effect on economic growth, technical and creative activities are proposed to be critical factors underpinning development success.

Hussain and Haque (2016) analyzed the relationship between Bangladesh's FDI inflows, trade transparency and economic growth cover the period 1973-2014 using the multivariate integration strategy. They found that there are major impact on economic growth on both FDI inflows and trade openness. Since foreign direct investment and trade are two main components of Bangladesh's economic development, it is important to frame policies that foster growth and reduce the barriers to capital flows. Chakraborty, and Reagle (2003) investigate the two-route association among FDI and economic growth for a board of 23 developing countries. Additionally, the impact of liberalization on the being of the connection between FDI and GDP is also being considered. For more open economies, they discover that the integrating vectors show bidirectional causal link GDP and FDI. The long-term causality is unidirectional for comparatively closed economies and runs from GDP to FDI.

Jevcak, Setzer & Saurdi (2010).analyzed FDI inflows in 10 new EU member countries in conditions of the unique characteristics of developing economies and the value of the framework of FDI. It was renowned that FDI inflow into these countries was attributed to country-specific causes, and behind this were the global driving forces. The findings revealed that faster growth and upper interest rates were linked to massive inflows of money. Capital inflows have, however, been found to be geared into the no tradable market. This indicates a lower contribution to the growth of production and the prospects for exports. Furthermore, in the case of a transition in the market atmosphere and risk assessment, a major capital inflow could be vulnerable to the economy.

Zhang, et al. (2001) and (Choe, 2003) additionally examined the connection between monetary development and FDI in other exploration. Zhang concentrated on data from developed nations, including Latin America and East Asia. And Zhang has observed that the studies indicate in many situations that FDI is profoundly enhancing the mechanism of growing economic growth, but there are two criteria beyond that and they are, whether the nation has macroeconomic stability, and trade regime. If these requirements are satisfied then FDI also had full effect on economic development. Choe (2003) examined the causality of foreign direct investment and economic growth in some cycle and found that economic growth actuates FDI.

2.4. The Empirical research on the effect of FDI on Economic growth

2.4.1. Positive Effects of FDI on Economic Growth

Jude and Levieuge (2017.) examined the impact of FDI on economic growth, based on the host countries' institutional consistency. To exhibit that auxiliary heterogeneity can be a clarification for the blended discoveries of past explanatory exploration, they set up a few hypothetical contentions. Utilizing a panel level regression model for an enormous example of developing countries, they uncovered that FDI flows just fundamentally increment a specific limit of institutional quality and have a significant positive effect on growth. To gain from FDI-led growth in order to, structural changes should therefore precede policies for attracting FDI. Moreover, some changes tend to support stronger marginal effects of FDIs, while structural complementarities may have a gradual influence on growth.

Chris Jones and Nigel (2013) researched the Contributions by FDI and ODA to economic growth of developed countries. To check the intrinsic endogeneities, they used a technique for the framework. The role of institutions, not just development and contact between institutions and other sources of growth, was also discussed. They find that, when institutions are taken into account, total foreign capital features a positive and substantial effect on growth. The effect on economic growth in Pakistan of foreign direct investment was investigated by Sohail,

and Azeem (2014). Investigated data from 2000 to 2010 using the simultaneous equation estimating approach of Two Stage least squares. The outcomes recommend that there is a positive connection between economic growth and FDI in Pakistan.

Ur Rahman (2014) investigate the effect of foreign direct investment on economic growth in f Pakistan with by data wiring from 1981 to 2010 As independent factors, foreign direct investment and the consumer price index were included. The outcome reveals that, while there is a negative link with CPI, there is a positive relationship between the FDI and GDP.

Gul and Imran (2015) used time series results from 2009 to 2013 to test the long- run link and association between co-integration research variables, regression method, correlation and Durbin Watson studies were used in the light of the impact of FDI and trade openness on Pakistan's economic development. Openness to FDI exchange and domestic capital has been shown to have a positive impact on economic growth.

Tshepo (2014) inspected the effect of FDI on economic growth and employment In South Africa for a period of 24 years from 1990 to 2013. The research used the Johansen Co-integration test the presence of a long-run relationship between the variables and the stationarity test of the unit root test. The outcome indicates that there was a positive long-run FDI relationship. Employment and GDP. The findings of the Granger Causality test confirmed the causal path that runs from FDI to GDP. The Theory of Modernization states that FDI in developing countries can contribute positively to economic growth. The demand for capital accumulation in developed nations can be fulfilled by FDI by capital spending, according to the Modernization Hypothesis, which can accelerate economic growth (Firebaugh, 1992).

Rahman & Chakraborty (2015) examined the connection between foreign direct investment and gross domestic product, they conducted analytical research in Bangladesh. FDI is an effective way of driving growth in the economy. FDI had a positive effect on economic growth as it contributed to the creation of HR and the implementation of advanced technology into the region. For the study of the pattern in GDP, they used secondary evidence. The upward trend was seen during the 1987-2011 period. They terminated that foreign investment inflows are very poor in Bangladesh (as a developing country) and that this situation is being improved by the government. Steps had to be taken, i.e. increasing labor skills, expanding infrastructure and addressing the issue of power shortages, an investment-friendly system, etc. Mello, (1999) who terminated that foreign investment in many developed nations is a significant factor in filling the capital gap. In South and East Asia, for instance, FDI has allowed economic growth by growing capital formation (Fry, 1999). Mohamed Amine (2012) found that, by using panel data estimate, FDI and ODA have a favorable and important effect on developed countries ' economic development. Adams. Found that DI has a positive and important effect on Sub-Saharan African countries economic development.

Mofrad (2012) found the results exist a positive and important long term connection between investment and export with gross domestic production. Romer (1993) investigated the international investment, such as highways and warehouses, is useful for constructing physical infrastructure. In exchange, enhanced physical facilities would increase the host country's adsorbent capacity, which will encourage more FDI. Kumar and Pradhan (2002) investigated the connection between FDI, growth and domestic investment for a sample of 107 developing nations for the 1980-99 period. As their independent variables, their model uses production flow as the dependent variable household and foreign owned capital stock, labor, human resources capital stock and total ingredient productivity. Their findings Exhibit the Panel Data estimates in the framework of the production function indicate a positive effect of FDI on growth, and although FDI seems to be crowding out domestic investments on a net basis, some countries have generally seen a positive impact of FDI on domestic investments on a net basis, indicating a role for host country policies. Hoang et al. (2010) analyzed effect of FDI on Vietnam's economic growth by using the 1995-2006 panel sample model across the sixty-one provinces of Vietnam. They find that FDI has a clear and optimistic influence on Vietnam's economic development as a conduit for rising capital stocks. Vietnam's human resources and trade are not yet the networks that provide access to modern technologies and information transfer from FDI inflows to support the economic development

of Vietnam. The effect of GDP and FDI and on the CPI of SAARC member country was undertaken by Abbas et al. (2011). The study concluded that a positive link between foreign direct investments has been established by the common model in these countries. The multiple regression models have tested this conclusion. In comparison, GDP, GNP, and PPP were seen to increase by FDI (Islam, 2012; Ahmed, 2005; Khan, 2007; Haque, 2007, Gupta, 1999, Kabir, 2007). In order to reduce the domestic savings shortfall, the foreign exchange shortage, the BOP deficit, the unemployment rate, the inflation rate and the poverty level, FDI also plays a role. The adoption of corporate social responsibility, the diversification of exports and the growth of financial institutions have also been related to FDI.

2.4.2. Negative Effects of FDI on Economic Growth

Ali Sharafat (2014). Found that FDI and inflation have negative long-term effects on Pakistan's economic growth. A unilateral causality operation from FDI, service debt and inflation and level of literacy to development was verified in the short-run research. He enabled use of the estimates and the evidence, Johansen co-integration methodology and the Granger causality were collected from 1972-2013. Dependency Theory suggests that foreign investment has a negative impact on the recipient country's economic growth. Diaz-Alejandro and Brecher (1977) endorse this theory, arguing that FDI will have a detrimental influence on the host country's economic development if the FDI-financed corporations repatriate disproportionate income to the parent country. This condition is known as benefit repatriation, which adversely influences the host country's BOP (Brecher & Diaz-Alejandro, 1977). Experts claim that by congestion out domestic spending, FDI has a detrimental impact on economic growth. Eller, Haiss, and Steiner (2005) observed, for instance, that international investment squeezed out domestic capital in a survey of eleven countries in Central and Eastern Europe. Lean and Tan (2011) observed that DI in Malaysia has a negative long-term effect on economic development. The same findings were informed by Aitken and Harrison (1999) who establish that foreign direct investment has a negative impact on the competitiveness of domestic companies in Venezuela's manufacturing sector. The proof of foreign investment remains unclear in the service sector. Agriculture and mining industries have no economic spillover capacity and FDI inflows are therefore of little performance. Similar experiments indicate different consequences of results of triggers. Some scholars claim that high GDP levels induce FDI inflows, while other papers say that economic growth is triggered by the FDI itself.

According to Achchuthan and Velnampy (2013), found the inflation have significant negative link with each other, also the inflation have significant impact on the economic growth. There is no significant link between inflation and economic growth in the Srilankan economic point of view. Quazi (2004) notes that due to capital flew, which is the outflow of domestic capital. FDI may have a negative impact on the host nation, resulting in an adverse effect on the current account and the foreign exchange rate of the government. FDI raises imports from the developing country because FDI-financed enterprises also demand high-tech capital equipment and intermediate commodities that are frequently not available in the host nation (Rahman, 2008).

2.5. Foreign Direct Investment & Its Components

Foreign direct investment in this research paper refers to an investment made by a consortium of businesses or individuals in one country, in particular an interest in a business or a benefit objective in another country, in the shape of setting up activities in another country, such as the ownership of a concern in a foreign corporation. Foreign direct investment needs, according to literature, a strong partnership between international firms and local companies. As this foreign direct commercial arrangement provides space for multinational corporations (MNC), this partnership promotes contracts between businesses. In a corporate company placed in a foreign market, a foreign direct investment corporation often has eligible voting rights. Expertise, monetary capital and machinery foreigners may also invest in an external business in their domestic countries by affirming the expenditure, economics and financial report of the economy, yet foreign direct investment. In the local companies set up to demonstrate percentage share, it is important to get from outside venture funds. New distribution outlets, new products and cheaper manufacturing facilities are produced by this international investment, having access to advanced technologies and learning new skills.

2.6. Summary of Literature Review

The relationship between FDI and economic growth has been concentrated by numerous scientists everywhere on the world up until now while the issue of FDI and economic growth is nonexclusive, for less developed countries, the association among FDI and economic growth is genuinely huge. There are a few unique economists experts who have utilized techniques to evaluate the connection between FDI and GDP in various nations around the globe. Authors also consistently agreed with each other, but others' results are not the same, even conflicting. In the recent literature of studies and outcomes of studies reported mixed outcomes, FDI and economic growth have been studied quite extensively, largely focused on emerging economies. Some of the studies analyzed the economic growth effect of foreign direct investment and found that with time lag, FDI had a significant and meaningful impact on economic growth in the host nation.

In addition, the effect of FDI differs with the capacity of local partners to take benefit of FDI's strategic advantages. The local regulatory system must, in particular, provide for economic conditions that are conducive to local enterprise, while minimizing the foreign investment firm's disproportionate market influence. In addition, local individuals and businesses must have the capacity to benefit from international investors.

Therefore, the impact of FDI is still contentious. In order to discover the effect of FDI on the economy, several studies have carried out. Some research have had positive impacts and others have seen negative impacts based on predicted factors, such As receiving countries, governance, economics and technical developments. FDI channels much-needed investment capital and encourages the formation of capital trade transparency promotes international capital flow and redirects factor enrichments to more gainful areas; a serious level of capital arrangement ensures the necessary subsidizing for the growth and development of industries and all of these jointly facilitate large-scale economic growth. The conclusive effects of FDI on economic growth as illustrated by the aforementioned literature review are largely ambiguous and thus the need for more research to determine the same.

3. OVERVIEW OF SOMALIA ECONOMY AND FDI PERFORMANCE

3.1. Overview of Somalia's Economy

Somalia is located in the "Horn of Africa," the easternmost tip of Africa. For millennia, it has been the gateway to Africa for business and trade. Somalia is a coastal nation located in Eastern African at the Horn of Africa which consists of Somalia, Ethiopia and Djibouti. Djibouti and Ethiopia border its northern and mid-western areas. Kenya is on its southern borders, and north of Somalia is the Gulf of Eden. Its eastern boundary makes up the Indian Ocean. Somalia is strategically positioned to bind individuals, enterprises and resources for all investors considering investing for foreign economic advantage and power in our many industries and sectors. Our power in agriculture, fisheries and livestock will help address the issues of many areas of the world over food security. A new era of inexpensive and sustainable energy can be led by our innovative wind and solar technologies to spur more economic development throughout the country.

A homogeneous community that shares a shared race, faith, and language is the people of Somalia's over 12 million population and the additional 2 million Diaspora live across the globe. The typical Somalis way of life is primarily nomadic pastoralists of riverine and inter-riverine sedentary groups who have systematically spread their mercantile culture to their neighbors.

The economy of Somalia rebounded in 2018 from the drought of 2016 to 17. Real GDP increased by an estimated 2.8 percent, up from 1.4 percent in 2017 but Lower than the preceding edition's prediction of 3.2 percent growth due to newly available trade and fiscal data for 2018 and a revised assessment of drought recovery. The recovery in agricultural production, domestic investment and ongoing remittances and donor inflows have contributed to the ongoing growth of remittances and donor inflows.

Somalia's economy depends vigorously on agribusiness, donor grants and diaspora remittances. Livestock is the biggest single sub-area supporter of GDP at 40% in 2018. Agriculture gives livelihoods to the greater part of the populace and creates between USD 250 – 350M every year, generally through trade with the Middle East. Services contribute marginally more than agriculture, and are driven by wholesale and retail trading, real estate, government services and Telecommunication. Money related administrations contribute very little to the GDP; this area is profoundly casual on the grounds that most of the populace spares outside the Banking system.

(AFDB, 2018)

Figure 3.1: Somalia Economic growth by sector, 2017/2018

Source: AFDB

3.2. Historical background of FDI inflow in Somalia

Somalia has undergone nine years of democratic rule and free market economy since its Independence Day (the year 1960-1969). International corporations controlled the economy of the country in general during this time, and public services in particular.

Fortunately, the military regime modified the institutions and practices of the region, which resulted in the nationalization and governance of all major industries and industries by government administrators. The nation witnessed the breakdown of all social services and equipment, including power, transportation, housing, health and education, following the fall of the society in the 1990s.

However, unlike public utilities, all services and infrastructure operated by private institutions were not lost and never failed, largely plundered (Argiolas, 2009).

According to the 2015 United Nations Conference Development, Somalia's FDI dropped slightly in 2014. The investigation shows that in recent years, Somali reported 7% in investment inflows to rake in US\$ 106 million compared to US\$ 107 attracted in 2013.

Low Somali FDI could result in a decrease in several variables, including additional sources of capital expenditure and foreign savings, as well as decreased productivity benefits, including work growth, technology transfer and related spillover effects, skills development, trade, competition and foreign market access. If Somali FDI increases, then these variables will increase. (United Nations, 2015). Somalia's economic growth is expected to be largely due to its development. This would contribute to an increase in Somalia's GDP. Somalia's economic development is low, because of the state breakdown that ruined the country's factories, social structures and properties, Somalia's economy consists of both traditional and modern production, but it relies more on customary production that makes the law to be the economic. The economic growth in the countries of East Africa is even higher than in Somalia. Since most industries are now being sluggish or because of less funding, their development is hampered.

3.3. Areas of Investment opportunities and Incentives

In Somalia, there is a possible investment opportunity to develop the following industries. It should be reminded that this list is not extensive but provides an overview of the most common possibilities for investment. Energy, telecommunications, agriculture, real estate, education, fishing, services and finance are among the sectors included. Also there is a competitive livestock market in Somalia and it is exported mostly to the Gulf countries. (Investment, Somalia Finance, 2019).

Figure 3.2 FDI distributions by sector, 2000-2018

3.3.1. Agriculture sector

The agriculture sector is a major contributor to Somalia's GDP. The livestock sub-sector, for example, is estimated to contribute over 30% of GDP and more than 50% of export earnings. However, owing to the use of antiquated techniques, such as inadequate field spacing, furrow planting and crop rotation, the agriculture sector is still marked by poor productivity. Furthermore, low productivity is due to insufficient access to financing, over-dependence on rain-fed agriculture in view of frequent droughts, dilapidated irrigation systems, inadequate or non-existent transport infrastructure, and disputed property rights. (Investment, financing in Somalia, 2019).

3.3.2. Fishing

The coast of Somalia is one of Africa's richest fishing grounds and holds tremendous promise for growth. Owing to a shortage of resource sand equipment and ineffective regulatory mechanisms, the industry has failed to grow. Investments in the fisheries sector will boost the health of coastal populations significantly.

3.3.3. Telecommunication sector

The Telecommunications industry also has many opportunities in the software and services market, as well as in expanding scope and penetration. It offers internet access at limited rates as well as other mobile telephone facilities. One of the most repeatedly used in Africa is mobile payment. Telecommunication Sector After the civil war some Somali citizen entrepreneurs set-up new businesses including telecommunication companies, to spring up the nation and contended to offer missing assistance. (Sarah and Nasir, 2010). Somalia also provides some of the world's most technologically sophisticated and competitively priced internet and telephone networks. These fledgling telecommunications companies, financed by Somali entrepreneurs and supported by ability from China, Korea and Europe, provide inexpensive cell phone and internet networks that are not accessible in many other areas of the continent. The private sector is primarily based on telecommunications, the internet, radio and television in the nation. In Somalia, Somali telecommunications enterprise also contribute services to each city and hamlet. In 2008, Dahabshiil purchased a controlling in Somtel, a Hargeisa-based telecommunications firm specialized in high-speed cable, mobile internet and mobile phone networks, as a global money transfer and banking company. The acquisition provided the necessary forum for Dahabshiil to subsequently broaden into mobile banking, a growing market in the regional banking sector. Investment in the telecom sector is considered to be one of the more clearly indicators that, amid civil wars in portions of the country, Somalia's economy has ongoing to rise. (Sarah C and Abdinasir 2010).

The sector offers essential connectivity services and promotes the production of jobs and the production of income in the process. The Somali Cabinet unanimous adopted the National Communications on March 22, 2012, which pavement the way for the creation the National Communications Authority, the national regulatory body for the telecommunications and broadcasting industries, for the time being. The Act is supposed to build an atmosphere conducive to investment, according to the Ministry of Information, Posts and Telecommunications, and the assurance it offers will facilitate more infrastructural growth, resulting in more effective delivery of services. Presently, at the finish of 2017, the National Communications Law is effective, operational and signed by the President.

3.3.4. Energy sector

Energy sector holds huge investment opportunities. Major legislation and changes are absent from the industry. These are ongoing and are planned in the immediate term to be in operation. As 1 kWh differs from US\$ 0.4 to 1 or over US\$ 1 in certain areas of the world, the cost of electricity is currently one of the highest compared to neighboring countries. Since lower electricity rates and electricity availability are critical for the region, as well as for the growth of local industry and manufacturing, energy is a high priority for key stakeholders and is needed to be dealt with accordingly. (Investment, financing in Somalia, 2019).

3.3.5. Transportation sector

Somalia is situated in the Horn of Africa and has an environment to encourage easy construction and facilitate the operation of transport infrastructure and have ample natural availability of building material inputs, while all local industries were closed later the civil war ruined in Somalia. In recent years, small factories have resumed and produced construction materials that are cheaper than imported materials from outside nations and particularly the major cities such as Mogadishu, Kismayo, Baidabo, Garowe, Hargeisa and Dhusamareb have been involved in beginning new buildings in the whole country. Security stability and based on federal representatives of states and federal government have been used by all these cities and they are constantly attracting new investment every year and the building of bridges, airports, ports and markets is growing suddenly. The overall governance and government system in Somalia is evolving as a result. The planning, intention and building of government buildings, utilities such as national roads and bridges, flood protection, water schemes and other public works is mandated by the Ministry of Public Work and Housing (MPWHR).

3.3.6. Manufacturing sector

Manufacturing sector is very vital for developing countries. It is considered as provide a source of jobs and optimistic spillovers (Tybout, 2000). In Somalia, before the civil war era, the history of manufacturing was genius and there were fifty-three independent, medium and large companies operating the sector. There was an opportunity for the nation to manufacture juices, textiles, canned meat, fruit and fish, beef, sugar, beverages, cosmetics, beverages, candy, etc. However, relative to historical experience and even to the countries in the region, it is actually so low and very few. Data from Somalia's customs show that Somalia has been steadily importing capital equipment for manufacturing and raw materials for the past three years.

This is an indicator that the prospect of production is brilliant for Somalia as a result of the entrepreneurial features of society. However, due to an uncertain and harsh climate with a cap on private investment, development still remains sluggish. These risks have made it impossible to draw investment in new technologies (World Bank, 2018). Mogadishu is surrounded by several light output factories. Foams, plastic elements, soft drinks and snacks, napkins, chairs, handmade garments, aluminum, bricks and interlocks, cement, shampoo and some cleaners and plastic bags. The government grants customs duty relief for their installation machines and tools to facilitate them and they are allowed a 50 percent reduction in customs duty on imports of raw materials from Mogadishu Port In different areas, for example, Somaliland and remaining states don't deliver more than previously mentioned items and even they do less.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Research Methodology

The purpose of this paper aim to examine the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth of Somalia (GDP), inflation rate, Domestic investments (DI) and GDP. Study covers the time period from 2000 to 2018.

4.2. Data Collection

The main type of data used in this study is secondary data, the empirical analysis is conducted by using annual data on FDI and economic growth in Somalia over the periods from 2000 to 2018 and unit of data is measured by millions of dollar currencies since Somali currencies is not working a well, after 1999 when central government was destroyed. The Data was collected from World Bank and SESRIC organization. Organization of Islamic countries forum especially statistical and social research.

4.3. Method of data analysis

In analyzing the dataset the following tests are expected to be employed: This study employed the augmented Dickey–Fuller [ADF], Philips– Perron [PP] to test for stationarity of the variables and Ordinary Least Square model was examined among dependent variable and independent variable.

4.4. Model Specification

The baseline model for this study can be represented as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$$

Where:

Y= Economic growth in Somalia as measured by absolute GDP values over the period.

X1=Foreign direct investment

X2=Inflation Rate

X3=Domestic Investment

α = constant

β = coefficient of the independent variable

ϵ = error term

5. DATA ANALYSIS, RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Analysis

To determine the growth trends of Somalia, FDI and inflation rate were analyzed on the basis negative and positive impact in the economy. Time series analysis was employed to display the trend of Somalia economic growth.

5.2 Time series Analysis

5.2.1 GDP

The figure below depicts trends of gross domestic product in Somalia from 2000 to 2018. From the time between 2000 and 2005, the trends of GDP in Somalia were consistent and tremendous growth occurred. The GDP fall in 2006 and immediately rise in 2007 with a proliferated and constant growth to 2009. After that, the GDP dropped down year after year to 2015. As at 2018 the GDP growth has not had massive growth as compared to 2009. As we can see, trends figure show that some years GDP were fallen recession and other years fallen to expansion growth.

Figure 5.1: Gross domestic product in Somalia from 2000 to 2018

5.2.2 FDI

The figure below presents the trends FDI inflows into Somalia from 2000 into 2018. The FDI inflows into Somalia started at low tone which was because inflation had ruin the growth of economy from 1980's to early 2000. FDI started rising 2006 to 2008 and declined 2009 in which the economy struggled to attract more investor into Somalia and it persisted till 2013 which made FDI positive but at low percentage impact in the economy. In 2014 Somalia started attracting FDI and this brought about tremendous increase. This graph also illustrates in 2014 FDI in Somalia had started to increase although after that time FDI sometimes fell to

recession and then gotten expansion. This has helped created job opportunities in the country and reduce poverty rate.

Figure 5.2: FDI inflows into Somalia from 2000 into 2018

5.2.3 Inflation rate

The figure below presents the trends inflation rate of Somalia from 2000 into 2018. The inflation rate of Somalia had positive digits since 2000 which has dampened the economic growth. Somalia has had the worst inflation rate between 2000 and 2018. The 2000 inflation rate was

3.36%.

Figure 5.3: Inflation rate of Somalia from 2000 into 2018

5.2.4 Domestic investments

This figure below presents the trends domestic investments of Somalia from 2000 to 2018. The trends domestic investments of Somalia had the worst trend even though it is positive digits since 2000s which has helped the economic growth in place of FDI. From 2000 to 2018 Somalia has had unpredicted trends of domestic investments growth on yearly basis.

Figure 5.4 Domestic investments of Somalia from 2000 to 2018

Prior to any econometric estimation on the time series variables, it is important to conduct stationary tests. This study employed the augmented Dickey–Fuller [ADF,] and Philips–

Perron [PP] to test for stationarity of the variables. For unit root test, the results shows that the null hypothesis of non-stationary at level for all the time series fails to be accepted. However, all null hypothesis were rejected for every test at first difference. It indicates clearly that all variables are stationary at (first difference).

Table 5.1.: A summary of unit root tests

Variables	ADF		PP	
	At level	1st difference	At level	1st difference
LGDP	-4.282354	-5.516809	-3.829076	-6.476134
LINF	-3.975783	-7.535721	-3.757915	-5.324907
LDI	-2.505102	-5.591476	-2.915375	-5.072355
LFDI	-5.291543	-7.101917	-3.981158	-6.790248

5.3. Regression Results

The OLS model was examined among dependent variable and independent variable.

Table 5.2: Model Summary

Model Summary					
M	R	R	Adjusted	Std.	Change Statistics

Model	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.591	.349	4670.95856	.349	2.683	3	15	.048

a. Predictors: (Constant), DI, FDI, Inflation

The R squared (R^2) value for this model is 34.9% implies that our independent variables explain about 34.9% systematic variation on the model over the observed year while the remaining variation is explained by other determinants variables outside the model counted in residual term e and also F-statistic are significant, so that this model has validity.

Table 5.3: Probability of the model

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	175620439.399	3	58540146.466	2.683	.048 ^b
	Residual	327267807.738	15	21817853.849		
	Total	502888247.137	18			

a. Dependent Variable: GDP
 b. Predictors: (Constant), DI, FDI, Inflation

Table 5.4: Estimates coefficient from the model

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	25128.219	4468.805		5.623	.000
	Inflation	-1338.590	1368.537	-.275	-.978	.043
	FDI	1.787E-5	.057	.463	2.043	.039
	DI	2.192E-5	.013	.395	1.500	.045

a. Dependent Variable: GDP

The result of the model shows that the coefficient of inflation rate ($b=-.275$, $p<.05$) indicating negative in the model, the study accept the hypothesis which predicted that inflation rate variable has negative relationship with economic growth, it means that one percent decrease will cause a change in the Somalia economic growth. FDI had positive and significant impact in the economy with ($b=.463$, $p<.05$) and domestic investment has positive and significant impact on GDP with ($b=.395$, $p<.05$).

5.4. Discussion

The study shows that inflation has negative relationship and significant effect on Somalia economic growth, this result was similarly in line with agrees by the study of Achchuthan, S and Velnampy. T, (2013). Found that inflation have the significant negative relationship with each other, also the inflation have significant impact on

the economic growth. This deters FDI into the country and so doing the economy loses lot of revenue and other operations which help boost the development and sustainability of a country.

The study shows that foreign direct investment has positive and significant effect on Somalia economic growth, this result was in line with the study of Rahman & Chakraborty (2015). It is of evidence that from 2000 to 2018 FDI has recorded positive growth in Somalia which has a greater impact in the economic growth and sustainability of the country. It is found that FDI positively affects GDP, which is in a form of employment generation for local people, which in the long run help unemployment and poverty reduction in Somalia.

The study shows that DI has positive relationship and significant effect on Somalia economic growth, this result was similarly found by those of Mofrad, (2012) who found the results that show a exist a positive and significant long term relationship between investment and gross domestic production. This therefore helps boost the economy by creating jobs locally and easing the government in terms of unemployment rate in the country. From 2000 to 2018 Somalia recorded massive DI which could not supplement the absence of FDI in the country.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

6.1. Summary and conclusion

Investments play an important role in economic development and the increase in assets and infrastructure in any developing nation. In an economy, direct investment is representative of a positive investment trend, ultimately resulting in a rise in the country's GDP and economic growth. This paper aim to investigate the effect of foreign direct investment on economic growth of Somalia for the period, which spanned between 2000 and 2018. In an economy, foreign direct investment is reminiscent of a positive pattern of investment which eventually interprets in the increment in GDP and economic growth of the nation. An Augmented Dickey–Fuller [ADF,]

Philips– Perron [PP] to test for stationarity of the variables and Ordinary Least Square model was used among dependent variable and independent variable.

The study also reveals that foreign direct investment has positive and significant effect on Somalia economic growth. Also the result shows that inflation has negative relationship and significant impact on Somalia economic growth. While Gross Domestic Investment has a positive relationship and significant impact on Somalia economic growth. Foreign direct investment in an economy shows that there is a decent quality pattern of investment which eventually brings about expanding the GDP in Somalia. The scope of this research was the period 2000-2018. For this period the study not tells what other research findings that hold in after 2018. The data use of the data from the various sources and that may differ from the other studies that use one source of the data and may become difference. Accordingly, the investigation suggests there is the requirement for the government to hold right monetary, fiscal policies and instruct the Somali worker to pull in the Somalia economy.

6.2. Recommendations for Future Research

The consequence of this study would be useful to foreign investors and development organizations seeking to better understand the role of FDI in Somalia. Based on the findings in this study and further to induce economic performance in Somalia, there is a requirement for the government to hold tight monetary and fiscal and train the Somali worker to draw in the Somali economy to pull in the Somali economy the following policies are proposed: There is a need for government to consciously pull foreign direct investment by previous of necessary infrastructure, which will lower the cost of doing business in Somalia.

Furthermore, Growth of any country depends upon the investments especial foreign investment, increasing assets and infrastructure. Foreign direct investment in an economy suggests that there is an investment pattern of good quality that eventually contributes to a rise in Somalia's GDP. Since there are no more studies in the domain of foreign direct investment in Somalia only this Paper is not enough and further research is needed. The Future research is advised to include other macroeconomic indicators (such as unemployment, gross national product and parity of purchasing power, poverty) which may help to better explain the effects of

foreign investment on Somalia's economic growth. Finally the government should support to solidness in macroeconomic factors and utilize such growth arranged and adjustment strategies particularly at large scale level which will initiate economic growth and improvement.

Bibliography

1. VO, Duc Hong, Zhaoyong Zhang, and Anh. Volatility and Disaggregated Supply Exports Exchange Rate: Empirical evidence from developing countries. *Journal of threat and Financial Management*. 2019:12:176
2. Silajdzic & Mehic. Knowledge Spillovers, absorbent Capacities and accomplish of foreign direct investment on Economic Growth, *Empirical Evidence from Transition Economies*, 2015:7:614-623.
3. Hussain & Haque. Foreign Direct Investment, Trade, and Economic development. *Empirical Analysis of Bangladesh Economies*, 2016:6:4-7
4. Chakraborty C, Reagle D. Liberalization, Foreign direct investment, and developing countries, a panel co-integration approach. *Economic Inquiry*. 2003:7:510-516
5. Zhang, P., Ding, S., Wang, G., & Zhou, D. An FDI approach for sampled-data systems. Paper provided at the American Control Conference.2001:6:2702-2707
6. Choe, J. I. Do FDI and gross domestic investment encourage economic growth.2003:7:44-57
7. Ridgeway, A. foreign direct investment concept (FDI) terms. Paper on Problems, Statistics Canada. 2004:11:1-7
8. OECD, foreign direct investment compromise and definitions 2012.
9. Nekipelov's, A. The Economic Growth Concepts: Mainstream approaches to macroeconomics and pure economics. "Moscow: School of Economics, Lomonosov, .Moscow State University.2011:1:18-30
10. Lequiller, François, and Blades, Derek, Economical, Paris. Includes CD-ROM.2004:12:246247
11. Tsikata, and T. The Link within the foreign exchange system and Eastern Africa macroeconomic results the International Monetary Fund, Working Paper.2012:12:1-4
12. Kamaludin & Mohamed. Feasibility of a monetary union: a model of dynamic panel regression in the East African community. *Financial, Business and Management Journal*. 2013:1:102-105
13. Buckley, Peter J., Jeremy Clegg, Changi Wang, and Adam Cross. FDI, regional differences and economic growth; Panel data evidence from China. *Transnet. Corp*. 2002:11: 1–28.
14. Bolbol, A. A., Fatheldin, A, and Omran, M. M. FDI, financial development, and economic growth; demonstrate from the Arab countries. *Rev; Middle East. Econ. Finance*. 2003:1: 31–49.
15. Jevcak, Setze, Suardi. Deciding factors of capital assist to the new EU member & during the financial crisis. *Management General Financial and Economic Affairs European Commission*; 2010:9:24-25

16. Jude & Leveuge. Growth impact of FDI in Developing Economies. *The World of Economy* 2017:4:15-42.
17. N, D' & Jones, C. I. Influence of foreign direct investment, Official development aid and immigrant remittances on economic Development in developing countries, Framework approach *The European newspaper of Development Research*, :2013:2:73-96.
18. Sohail, H Y. Suhail, A and Azeem. Effect of FDI on Economic Growth in Pakistan, *World Diary of Economic and Finance*.2014:1:2-5.
19. Ur Rahman, Z. Influence of FDI on Economic development in Pakistan newspaper of *Economic and Sustainable Development*.2014:5: 251-255.
20. Gul, K M. and Imran, N. Impact of FDI on Economic development of Pakistan, *American newspaper of trade and Management*.2015:4:190-202
21. Tshepo. M. The effect of FDI on Economic Growth Employment in South Africa a Time cover Study, *Medlar newspaper of social sciences*.2014:5:18-27.
22. Firebaugh, G. Growth Effects of FDI. *American Journal of Sociology*, 1992:105–130.
23. Rahman, A., & Chakraborty, S. Impact of FDI on GDP Developing countries' empirical evidence. *Advances in Economics and Business*, 2015:3:587–592.
24. Mello and Jr. Foreign direct investment-led growth: facts from time cover and panel data. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 1999:1:133–151.
25. Adams, Samuel. FDI, domestic investment, and economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa 2009:5:178-183.
26. Mofrad, M. A. The link between export and GDP in IRAN. *Business Intelligence Journal*. 2012:7:2-5.
27. Romer, .P Idea gaps and of artifacts gaps in economic development. *Newspaper of Monetary Economics*, 1993: 2: 543–573.
28. Kumar, Nagesh and Pradhan, Jaya Prakash. Foreign Direct Investment, Externalities, and Economic Growth in Developing Countries, Some Empirical studies and effect for WTO negotiate on Investment. *Paper for debate*.2002:4:1-7
29. Hoang. Does Foreign Direct Investment Encourage Economic Growth in Vietnam? *Asian Economic Bulletin*, 2010: 27: 295-311.
30. Islam, A. M. A preliminary investigation of the U.S. foreign assistance to Bangladesh. Retrieve from.2012:30:1-8.
31. Ali, Sharafat, examine of Financial progress and Economic Growth in Pakistan.2014:29:193201
32. Dutt, A, K. The standard of foreign direct investment and economic growth. *World Development*, 1997:25(11) 1925–1936.

33. Lean & Tan. Linkages Among foreign direct investment, domestic investment and economic growth on Malaysia, 2011:10: 75–96.
34. Abbas, Q., Akbar, S., Nasir, A., Amanullah, H. & Naseem, M. Impact of Foreign Direct Investment. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*. 2011:5:1-27
35. Brecher, R. A., & Diaz-Alejandro, C. F. Tariffs, Foreign Capital, and Immiserating Growth. *Journal of International Economics*, 1977:7:317–322.
36. Eller, M., Haiss, P., & Steiner, K. FDI in the financial sector. The engine of growth for central and eastern Europe? *Europe Institute Working Paper No. Business Administration*. 2005:12:169
37. Achchuthan, T & Velnampy. Fiscal Deficit and Economic Growth: A Study on Sri Lankan Economic Perspective, In *Developing Country Studies*. 2013:3:166-174.
38. Quazi, R. M. Foreign assistance and capital flight; an analysis of a case of Bangladesh. *Newspaper of the Asia Pacific Economy*, 2004:1:370–393.
39. Rahman, K. M. A. globalism and the climate of Foreign Direct Investment, An analysis of the case for Bangladesh. *Publication of Investment and Banking*. 2008:5
40. Fry, M. Some instruction for South Asia from developing country encounter with foreign direct investment. *The World Bank*, 1999:11:30 Washington D.C.
41. Aitken & Harrison. Do domestic companies advantage from Foreign Direct Investment, Evidence from Venezuela, 1999:6:605-618
42. Argiolas, & Floris, Construction inventive models of territorial governance. *Newspaper of Place Management and Development*. 2009:10: 178-210.
43. African Development Bank Group, (2018).
44. United Nations conference on trade, and development (2015)
45. Investment, Financing in Somalia (2019)
46. Somalia Transport Sector Needs Assessment and Investment Programmer, African Development Bank Group. 2016:10:1-9
47. Tybout, J. R. Manufacture Firms in Developing Countries, *Journal of Economic Literature*. 2000:3:11-4
48. Hassan, A. A., Mohamed, M. M., Isak, N. N., & Mohamed, S. B. Export achievement and Economic Growth, Fragile Economies. The Case of Somalia. *Academic Research International*. 2018:108-117.
49. Mohamed, Isak, N.N. and Roble, D.H., private sector developments of Somalia investigation on some major sectors. 2014:10:3-10.